

**PEDAGOGICAL AND PSYCHOLOGICAL FACTORS OF THE
FORMATION OF ATTITUDES TO A HEALTHY LIFESTYLE OF YOUNG
PEOPLE IN THE FAMILY**

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Annotation: Providing insights into the pedagogical and psychological factors of the formation of attitudes towards a healthy lifestyle of young people in the family.

Key words: Family life, family relationship, lifestyle, healthy environment.

In fact, the family is a place of education where the human qualities, virtues, and values that are formed in every person from early childhood are perfected, and which ensures the development of the values and spiritual heritage of the Uzbek people, which have been formed for thousands of years." All human qualities, such as honesty, truthfulness, honor, modesty, kindness, hard work, are formed, first of all, in the family." When we talk about family, first of all, the image of mother is formed in our eyes. The first factor that ensures the sanctity of the family is the purity, intelligence, kindness, loyalty and loyalty of the mother, the woman." the values of the higher class harmonize in their mutual relations and create a ritual of mutual relations in the family. This social process in the family shows the young generation's imaginations, views, concepts, worldviews about the material world, social life, and Eastern etiquette rules and the correct guidelines for their practical observance. The spiritual image of the young generation, their behavior and

behavior are initially formed in the culture of family relations). Historical data show that the culture of family relationships is a social reality that has developed in the eastern nations since ancient times. The rules of etiquette, norms, which are manifested in the works of the ancient peoples, in sacred religious sources, in the masterpieces of the oral creativity of the Uzbek people, in the works of the great thinkers of the East, especially in the family interpersonal relations characteristic of the Uzbek people, you can find valuable information about the expression of human qualities. In the sources, the unimaginability of human life without a family, the perfect upbringing of children, the culture of husband and wife and mutual relations in it, the ways of a happy and prosperous marriage, are described in the form of wisdom and advice with the help of life examples.

Today, important work is being done in our Republic to study the family lifestyle and create a healthy lifestyle in the family. These tasks and problems serve as an important factor in the family's health, moral and economic well-being, and the upbringing of children. The reason is that a lifestyle based on active creativity means social activity in all areas of society, high quality of citizenship, mental, spiritual and physical health, high civility in work, interaction, communication, looking at negative events with intolerance and fighting against them. , embodies qualities such as reasonable attitude towards nature, kindness to others. In fact, a healthy lifestyle in the family serves to further strengthen the social status of people in society. Because lifestyle is inextricably linked with people's spiritual world and plays an important role in their way of thinking.

- Philosophical, spiritual and psychological criteria of a healthy lifestyle can be described as follows:
- paying special attention to the dressing of young girls and women in the family, educational institutions and public places;
- to widely promote the unique traditions and values of our people regarding healthy living, the teachings of fathers and mothers, and the experience of individual healthy spiritual families in the formation of the behavior culture of young people in the family and in public places;
- use of the activities carried out in our country and the traditions of family sportsmen to form a positive attitude of young people to sports, including family sports;
- formation of a culture of understanding the essence of life, honoring the value of life, rational organization of life activities among family members, first of all among young people;
- formation of social opinion about the values of water, air, land and water by promoting the principles of mediocrity and decency in Islamic philosophy among the masses. In general, the formation of the philosophy of health is directly related to healthy and folk rituals, traditions and permanent national values.¹

The fact that such internationally significant events are on the agenda indicates that issues such as family life, the strength of interpersonal relations in it, and its well-being are extremely urgent problems as the main category of social

¹Саидов А.И. Оилада ёшларнинг соғлом турмуш тарзи тўғрисидаги тасаввурларни шакллантиришнинг ижтимоий-психологик хусусиятлари. Психол.ф.д.илмий даражасини олиш учун ёзилган дисс. – Т.,2020 й

psychology and the basis of interpersonal relations. " In the East, the family has been considered a sacred homeland since ancient times. If the family is healthy and strong, peace and harmony will be achieved in the neighborhood. Therefore, peace and stability will prevail in the state only if the neighborhood and the country are strong." It can be seen that the issues of family life are becoming one of the priority areas of modern scientific research. The establishment of the scientific and practical center "Family" in our republic and the adoption of the "Family Code" (1998) by the government are among the important practical works being done today to maintain the strength and stability of families. Unfortunately, the weakening of family-marriage relations by the present time is evident in almost most countries of the world: the United States of America, England, France, Germany, the Baltic states, Russia and a number of other countries. Uzbek families Although the weakening of family-marriage relations and its violations are much less than in the above-mentioned countries, unfortunately, it is observed that the complications of divorce cause extremely sad consequences, unpleasant situations and events between family members and relatives. Therefore, the breakdown of families and the various complications that arise as a result of it require extensive study as a research subject of social psychology and ethnopsychology. In order to create a clearer picture of this issue among our young people, we will compare the differences between their peers 90-100 years ago, that is, between 15-16-year-old boys and girls at the beginning of our century and today.

In conclusion, it can be said that according to what is written in the special literature and the results of the conducted research, according to the acceleration process observed in people in the last 100 years, their sexual and physiological

puberty has been advanced by 2-3 years. About 100 years ago, the period of puberty of young people was 15-16 years old, and now it is 12-13 years old on average. Now we will consider the aspects of readiness of these young people for family life. After 11 years of compulsory education for all, a certain part of our youth continues their studies in higher educational institutions. It can be seen from this that the economic independence of our youth is reached at the age of 20-21 for some of them, and at 23-25 for others. In addition, along with the development of people's lifestyle, the daily life of their families changes, the need for clothing, household goods, and the level of material well-being also increases.

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